

PUHURI Deliverable D.A1.1 Current Status report

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Abstract

Deliverable D.A1.1 Current state report addresses the current state of Puhuri project, covering the state of its stakeholders (service providers, resource allocators, MyAccessID AAI users), architecture, business model including the current cost structure and GDPR compliance.

Puhuri has already shown its importance and potential on a European level by producing services used by over 25 organisations in the Nordic and Central European region. When interviewing a selection of organisations the project received positive feedback on the services provided by Puhuri and also improvement feedback.

Puhuri is currently onboarding new service providers and resource allocators and for that contracts as well as legal and governance structure is being prepared. In its current state Puhuri is not a separate legal entity, which leads to certain hindrances with the scalability of the system, including contract issues and the future governance of the system. One objective of the Puhuri project is to define and implement a scalable governance structure.

Main key points

Where we are at the moment:

- Puhuri is used by EuroHPC LUMI as the main access method connecting it with resource allocators in many countries.
- Puhuri provides a set of services for supporting resource allocation: Puhuri Core, Puhuri Portals, Puhuri Stats, and support.
- We are working on defining governance as well as sustainability models for Puhuri.
- A number of contractual models and their GDPR-impact has been analysed and we are in the process of selecting the most scalable one.
- Initial business model is introduced based on a cost sharing model.

Methodology, activities and materials used to develop this deliverable are :

1. Previous public documents produced by the Puhuri 1 project as well as the on-going work of the Puhuri 2 project that has not yet been published in the deliverables.
2. Data from the Puhuri Core, which was aggregated and anonymised.
3. 9 interviews were performed for this deliverable. Interviews were constructed in a semi-structured way with a fixed set of questions with follow-up questions. Respondents interviewed were Puhuri stakeholders and users of the Puhuri Portal.

Introduction

Puhuri is a solution for resource allocation, project management, and accounting coupled with an infrastructure for authentication and authorisation (AAI). *Puhuri's vision is to provide seamless access to pan-European computing and HPC adjacent services for researchers and industrial users.*

In the first phase (Puhuri-project, 2019-2022) the aim was to develop a solution for LUMI, the first pre-exascale EuroHPC supercomputer in operation. In the second phase (Puhuri 2 -project, 2022-2025) the aim is to widen the scope to cover multiple EuroHPC and other resources, but also to introduce new features and services. Puhuri already provides users, resource allocators, and resource providers with a simple but powerful system where the individual needs of these groups are addressed.

Puhuri development is funded by NeIC (Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration). The project partners cover research e-infrastructures representing their countries.

First Puhuri-project deliverables

- Deliverable 1: *Requirements collection and technical architecture plan. Designing the technical architecture and gathering the requirements from different stakeholders.* The first terminology for Puhuri was composed¹.
- Deliverable 2: *Implementation of Puhuri core functionalities.* Describes the implementation of the Puhuri core functionalities for authentication, authorization and resource allocation².
- Deliverable 3: *LUMI integration to Puhuri LUMI EuroHPC supercomputer is the primary use case for Puhuri.* LUMI consortium countries may integrate their national portal to Puhuri or use Puhuri provided portal to manage the LUMI projects. As an example, Swedish SUPR portal integration is discussed³.
- Deliverable 4: *Accounting and Reporting Accounting information collection into Puhuri Core and Swedish SUPR portal integration to fetch accounting data.* An early version of Puhuri Statistics web portal is also presented there⁴.

The system provided by the first Puhuri project is a critical component for LUMI, and as such Puhuri must be available at least throughout the lifetime of LUMI (2026). Moreover, Puhuri has been approached and is approaching several other entities expressing an interest in Puhuri services. Puhuri 2 -project will develop new, and consolidate existing services needed by current and future customers of Puhuri, e.g., EuroHPC LUMI⁵, EuroHPC LUMI-Q and NeIC NordiQuEst⁶. This will require a governance model flexible enough to meet needs of stakeholders while compliant with relevant regulations and frameworks, including GDPR and funding models. In order to provide these services to a multitude of target customers, the sustainability and scalability of Puhuri must be ensured, which is part of the work to be done in Puhuri 2.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288776>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727686>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5747047>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361321>

⁵ <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/eurohpcju/>

⁶ <https://neic.no/nordiquest/>

Puhuri 2 will strengthen international collaboration with research infrastructures, HPC centres, and other stakeholders, and will work together with European actors to further the federation of European computational resources. Puhuri 2 has the ambition to collaborate and align with other infrastructures and AAI systems such as FENIX⁷ and Life Science AAI⁸ as well as the federation of AAIs via EOSC. Other stakeholders with no computational use-case of LUMI, e.g., services sustained from the EOSC-Nordic⁹ project, can benefit from solutions developed by Puhuri and promote their adoptions.

The goal of the Puhuri 2 Project is

1. To continue operating the Puhuri solution.
2. To broaden the customer base potentially adding new features as needed, and
3. To ensure the sustainability of Puhuri by identifying potential future recipients of the system and establishing a robust hand-over process.

According to the Puhuri 2 -project plan, the following themes are in the scope of Activity 1:

- Contracts
- Transfer of ownership
- Organisational and project steering roles (including collaboration with other NeIC projects)
- Support for the forming of policies, methodologies, and collaborations
 - a. Funding agencies & policy makers: NeIC, EuroHPC JU
- Creation of a transferral process of the system, from development into governance and operations, founded in a transparent and robust process and methodology¹⁰
- Cost structure awareness

1. Service description

1.1. Target customer group

Puhuri's customers are resource allocators (e.g. universities) and service providers (e.g. LUMI EuroHPC supercomputer). Puhuri users are researchers or industry professionals aiming to have access to LUMI and in the future also to additional HPC, quantum or other resources.

1.2. Benefits of using Puhuri

Advantage of using Puhuri services is reduced administration costs of service providers. Using Puhuri Portal is an option to avoid operating their own resource allocation portal. The portal can be branded for their organisation. There is also the option to integrate the existing portal with Puhuri Core and thus allow users to use a portal familiar to them.

⁷ <https://fenix-ri.eu/>

⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/compute/aa>

⁹ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

¹⁰ Not covered in this deliverable

Using the federated services for Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) allows end-users of the systems to authenticate with their identity providers. Services can integrate with Puhuri AAI allowing them to avoid managing passwords for the end-users and should users leave an organisation their affiliation attribute will change and service providers can react to that.

1.3. Puhuri funding and service delivery

Puhuri development and operations are currently funded mainly by NeIC and the project partners.

Responsibilities of the service delivery:

- University of Tartu provides Puhuri Core and Puhuri portal hosting services to service providers and resource allocators, which also includes support;
- GÉANT provides Puhuri AAI and MyAccessID.

1.4. Architecture

Puhuri Service components are:

- Puhuri AAI is the federated authentication and authorization infrastructure
- Puhuri Core consists of the resource allocations database
- Puhuri Portals for the resource allocation, group management and reporting
- Statistics portal for specific reporting for the service providers
- Puhuri helpdesk: customer support for Portals, Core and Puhuri AAI L1.

Figure 1: The user is interacting with the national portal or Puhuri Portal depending from which Resource Allocator (call) they are applying resources.

When Resource Allocators accept the request, that is pushed to the Puhuri Core and further to the Service Providers. A user can use federated authentication to login to the resource allocation portals and possibly also the resources if they have been integrated into Puhuri AAI.

1.4.1. Puhuri AAI

Puhuri AAI is one of the essential Puhuri Service components as it enables Users to access resources such as LUMI securely. Work within the Puhuri project AAI task started with defining technical and organisational requirements for Puhuri AAI (Laitinen et al., 2020).

Figure 2.: AAI components and connection to other Puhuri service components.

The user gets a Puhuri user identity by registering in the MyAccessID service operated by GÉANT eduTEAMS. During the registration, the user accepts the Terms of Use conditions. Users can also add a public ssh key(s), which is propagated to resource providers among the other user's personal data. Academic users typically use a home organisation identity provider (IdP) to authenticate themselves via MyAccessID Idp Proxy. In this manner, the user does not need a new password for the services. Since not all end-users come from organisations that have their Idp integrated into eduGAIN federation, there

are also two alternative solutions available in the IdP discovery services namely European eIDAS, where there are at the moment 13 European countries, which offer national authentication solutions. As a last resort, there is the Swedish eduID.se service, which offers registration by email with the eIDAS identity vetting option.

If a Service Provider would like to use Puhuri AAI as an authentication method, then it should fill in the registration web form, where the service provider needs to provide organisational information as well as policy documents. There may be a fee depending on the contract with the University of Tartu.

Puhuri and GÉANT have been actively encouraging the national federations to support and push the identity providers to provide a level of assurance attributes for the user, indicating the method of how the user's identity was ensured. For example, Google as an identity provider does not do identity vetting e.g. based on banks' authentication or passport.

In MyAccessID and Puhuri AAI, there are Acceptance and Production environments. Acceptance environments are mainly used for beta integrations (see Chapter 1.5 - Onboarding process). Production environments are meant for normal operations with real live data.

1.4.2. Puhuri Portals

Puhuri portals are meant for Resource Allocators and end users. Resource Allocators can create projects and allocators for the project PIs and approve or reject the resource allocation requests from the project PIs. In addition to that, allocators and PIs can manage project membership - invite users or remove them. Both of these roles can check the usage of approved allocations.

Currently, Puhuri provides four dedicated portals and one shared portal. Portal improvement is a continuous process together with the portal users.

1.4.3. Puhuri Core

Puhuri Core is the central component of Puhuri and it has an API for the portal and service provider integrations. Those are described in puhuri.neic.no technical documentation. Puhuri Core receives resource allocations with the project information including the members from the resource allocation portals. This information is then fetched by the Service Provider to whom the allocation is targeted. Service Providers may also use scripts to fetch the information into their local user management system. The Service Provider sends the accounting information to Puhuri Core from where the portals may fetch the information and present it to their users.

Puhuri Core is also integrated with the Puhuri statistics portal (see following chapter 1.4.4) to present more detailed information about accounting and reporting.

This central component of Puhuri services is multi-tenant, which may be connected with several service providers and client allocation portals. Technology-wise, it uses the same software as Puhuri portals but is configured slightly differently.

1.4.4. Puhuri Statistics

Puhuri Statistics is a Grafana¹¹ portal aggregating resource consumption information for service providers and resource allocators. The reporting can be tailored based on the needs. For example, in the LUMI case, the reporting is tailored for the LUMI project office so that they can follow the different utilisation and amount of users, who are in the LUMI projects.

Roles for Puhuri statistics are taken from the Puhuri Core. This means that for example as a RA, you will see your organisation-related projects' usage.

The Puhuri statistics environment is improved continuously based on the received feedback.

1.5. Customer onboarding process

This section describes the planned customer onboarding process.

The Puhuri onboarding process will consist of four steps:

- Request and approval
- Beta environment(s) integration
- Contracting
- Production integration

New customers should decide which Puhuri service components they would like to use. They can choose the whole set, which includes Puhuri AAI and Puhuri Core or some service components alone. When Puhuri receives the request to join, then this request is forwarded to the Steering Group. After checking the details, the Steering Group may approve or reject the request. The request must contain information about:

- Service description and reason for joining
- Service provider legal data (address, contact information, etc.)

If the request is approved, then beta integration will start. This may include AAI Beta environment, Puhuri Core Beta environment integration or both. This step needs work from both sides - the Puhuri team and the new customer. In this process, the new service provider should provide additional technical details for integration with Core. Again, when everything works on the beta level, the next step is contracting. The Puhuri team prepares the operational contract based on the information received from the new service provider. When the contract is signed, the production integration will take place.

As of November 2022, Puhuri is onboarding a new customer - both Service Provider and Puhuri AAI user — Riga Technical University (RTU). RTU is one of the largest Latvian universities and is investing in upgrading its HPC centre and services. Latvia is closely connected to other NeiC countries for instance as a part of EOSC-Nordic and has joined the Puhuri project as an observer.

¹¹ <https://grafana.com/>

Figure 3: The onboarding process.

1.6. SLA, service hours

University of Tartu provides SLA for hosted Puhuri portals and Core. Every service component hosted by University of Tartu is monitored and in case of service delivery failure, immediate actions are taken. These actions include communication with affected parties, issue root cause investigation and fixing. SLA conditions depend on the agreements with the customers.

1.7. Division of responsibilities (customer's duties vs. Puhuri)

The table below describes examples of the main tasks and responsible party for the activities to fulfil a particular task. For now, Puhuri's operating and hosting organisation is the University of Tartu, so all contracts are signed with this entity. The second party is the Customer, in example below - Service Provider - which can be the resource allocator or the service provider. Based on the role, tasks and activities are slightly different.

Task	New customer responsibilities	Puhuri responsibilities
Puhuri Core - Service Provider integration. Includes Beta integration.	Responsible for the integration work with Puhuri Core. Provides the terms of use documentation.	Provides API documentation.
Puhuri Core - national portal integration.	Responsible for the integration work with Puhuri Core.	Provides API documentation.
Puhuri Core - self-hosted Puhuri portal integration.	Responsible for the integration work with Puhuri Core.	Provides API documentation.
Puhuri Core - UT-hosted Puhuri portal integration.	Provides organisational details for white labelling.	Responsible for the integration work with Puhuri Core.
Contracting	Provides contracting information.	Prepares the draft contract based on information from the new customer.
AAI registration.	Fills out the AAI registration form.	Provides the form URL to be filled.
AAI integration for the national portal.	Responsible for the integration work.	
AAI integration for the Puhuri portal.		Responsible for the integration work.
UT-hosted Puhuri portal setup (incl privacy policy and terms of use).	Provides the organisational information for privacy policy and terms of use.	Prepares the portal.

Self-hosted Puhuri portal (incl privacy policy and terms of use).	Prepares the portal.	Provides the documentation.
Support		Provides support for the service provider and level 1 support for the AAI issues.

Figure 4: Share of responsibilities

1.8. Technical documentation and marketing site

Puhuri team has prepared a detailed documentation site¹² for Puhuri’s customers. This means that Service Providers, Resource Allocators, and end users can also find well-documented instructions for different scenarios. These include integration instructions, AAI account registration, user guides for project and allocation creation, etc.

For marketing, we are developing a landing page¹³ for Puhuri. The preliminary version is out, but soon version 2 will be launched.

1.9. Use case scenarios

- **Requesting the resources:** As a User, I can create a project and request resources by using the national allocation portal or the Puhuri portal. For shared and dedicated Puhuri portals, we have created user guides, which help end-users. The shared portal guide¹⁴ is [here](#) and the dedicated portal guide¹⁵ is [here](#).
- **Managing group memberships:** As a Project Manager (Principal Investigator), I can invite or remove users to my project and assign a co-PI role for those who can do similar operations as I by using the resource allocation portal.
- **Accepting resource allocations:** As a Resource Allocator, I can view and accept or reject the resource allocation in my Puhuri Portal instance.
- **Accessing Service Provider:** As a User, I can authenticate to service. In case service provider support login with the ssh key, Puhuri supports the method that the users add their SSH key to the MyAccessID user profile¹⁶. If the service is integrated with SAML2/OIDC protocol, then the user would use MyAccessID Idp proxy to authenticate to the service. LUMI Support Team has prepared a user guide¹⁷ for logging in to LUMI. This can be found [here](#).
- **Project accounting information:** As a User or Resource Allocator I can view the resource consumption in the Puhuri Portal or national portal. This information is sent by the service provider via Puhuri Core.

¹² <https://puhuri.neic.no/>

¹³ <https://puhuri.io>

¹⁴ https://puhuri.neic.no/user_guides/user_guide_shared/organization_and_project_management_shared/#creation-of-projects

¹⁵ https://puhuri.neic.no/user_guides/user_guide_dedicated/organization_and_project_management/#creation-of-projects

¹⁶ <https://mms.myaccessid.org/fed-apps/profile/>

¹⁷ <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/firststeps/loggingin/>

- **Statistics information:** As Service Provider I can have a view of the resource allocation status for the different resource allocators of my resource.

1.10. Discussion & future scenarios

The Puhuri project plans to implement a Resource Application Review Process support for the Puhuri Portal in 2023. Users would not need to use a different portal or email-based application submission method. This would also streamline the process avoiding typing the same information twice.

Puhuri wishes to integrate with the EuroHPC application portal, so the service providers integrated with Puhuri would receive the decided resource into Puhuri Core. This requires political decisions and technical implementation from the peer review portal.

In January 2023, the Puhuri team plans to launch a new theme for portals, which will improve the user experience.

2. Status of agreements

2.1. IPR and licences

In general, the Puhuri Collaboration Agreement defines that the results are owned by the party or parties that have generated them. In addition, NeIC owns the Puhuri brand.

The licensing for some of the artefacts that Puhuri is relying upon is as follows:

- Puhuri Core / Portal is based on the Waldur platform¹⁸, which is released under MIT licence.
- Puhuri Stats is built using Grafana - AGPL licence - and Prometheus - Apache2 licence.
- Puhuri Support is based on Atlassian Servicedesk, which is a proprietary service.
- Microservice for integration of Puhuri Core with LUMI RT is released under GPL because of the RT GPL-licensed library.
- SNIC portal integration code with Puhuri Core is proprietary and maintained by SNIC.
- LUMI (Service Provider) integration with Puhuri is proprietary and maintained by CSC.
- Puhuri documentation is public and licensed under Creative Commons.

2.2. Operational agreements with Service Providers

Today, the University of Tartu is the main point of contact for making contracts with Puhuri customers, and coordinating the financial flows regarding customer contracts and service delivery. This is seen as a temporary solution. Currently, there is no legal entity dedicated specifically to Puhuri, and it is essential to define the future legal frame to efficiently manage IPR and contracting issues.

¹⁸ <https://waldur.com/>

Service Provider makes an operational contract with the University of Tartu. This agreement states which Puhuri service components are offered to the Service Provider. It includes Puhuri Core and Puhuri statistics portal access, as well as Service Desk. It also contains a more detailed SLA matrix. In addition to the main body of the agreement, it has several appendices like

- Personal Data Processing Agreement;
- Service fees and payment terms;
- Service description;
- Technical and organisational measures of Puhuri Core.

2.3. GDPR

Today, Puhuri handles the data of thousands of users. The main principle of GDPR is data minimization i.e. avoiding storing or distributing unnecessary data, limiting access to the data only for the necessary people and removing the data when it is not needed anymore. Since the LUMI supercomputer is currently the only resource provided via Puhuri, most contracts relate to LUMI. Regarding GDPR, LUMI consortium has a shared controllership for user data and CSC is mandated to make contracts on behalf of the consortium, e.g. service delivery with University of Tartu.

When scaling up the Puhuri service, especially the GDPR model requires special attention. The short-term plan for GDPR-related roles and contracts is the following:

- 1) Customer (Resource Provider or Resource Allocator) is a data controller for their users. Customers are the ones who decide why the data is collected, and how it will be used.
- 2) University of Tartu is a data processor for Puhuri service delivery as in its entirety. UT does not use the data for other purposes than serving their customers. UT makes contracts with each customer separately.
- 3) GÉANT is a data controller for Puhuri AAI
- 4) GÉANT is a data controller for MyAccessID, as they are using it for other purposes as well and the user accepts the conditions separately.

In the long run, however, this model is not suitable for scaling up. The GDPR model will be developed together with other contracting issues. Eventually, there should be a dedicated legal entity to manage the contracts between customers and Puhuri service delivery.

2.4. Privacy Policy and Terms of Use docs

We have prepared the privacy policy¹⁹²⁰ and terms of use²¹²² documents for both Puhuri Core and Puhuri Portal. Privacy policy documents mainly describe, which kind of personal data we process and also define the roles according to GDPR. In the shared Puhuri portal, which is hosted for the countries,

¹⁹ <https://puhuri-core.neic.no/policy/privacy/>

²⁰ <https://puhuri-portal.neic.no/policy/privacy/>

²¹ <https://puhuri-portal.neic.no/tos/>

²² <https://puhuri-core.neic.no/tos/>

which do not have a national portal or dedicated Puhuri portal, the University of Tartu agreed to take the data controller role, otherwise, the University of Tartu is the data processor.

2.5. Discussion & future scenarios

Today, the University of Tartu is the main point of contact for making contracts with customers, and for coordination of the financial flows regarding customer contracts. This is seen as a temporary solution. There is no legal entity dedicated specifically for Puhuri, and it is essential to define the future legal frame to efficiently manage IPR and contracting issues. Most of the current contracts are directly or indirectly linked with CSC/LUMI, or they are in the form of MoU. This is of course not a sustainable model in the long run, when services and operations are scaled up.

One option is to establish a legal entity to take care of contracting issues, working as a one stop shop, and leading the participation to e.g. funding calls. Also other options are studied.

It is also vital to work together with other European stakeholders, such as EOSC, GÉANT, Fenix RI and EuroHPC JU in order to develop an interoperable European framework to share resources, manage projects, and manage user identification in an efficient and user-friendly way.

3. Business model

3.1. Cost structure

The Puhuri cost structure can be divided into four main categories:

- 1) Operative costs to deliver the service
 - a) IT costs related to service delivery (e.g. Puhuri AAI with GÉANT, software costs, server/hardware costs)
 - b) User support
 - c) DevOps cost
- 2) Integration cost to add new customers on-board
 - a) Communication, planning and management with the customer
 - b) Technical integration work
- 3) Development costs to push the solution and service further
 - a) Mainly personnel costs; depends on the nature of the project
- 4) Administrative cost
 - a) Management and coordination
 - b) Sales and marketing
 - c) Contract management
 - d) Other overhead (premises, etc)

Most of these costs are not depending on the number of customers/users. Hence, the more there are customers, users and other stakeholders, the more cost-efficient Puhuri makes the resource allocation at the European level.

3.2. Pricing

The pricing model for each service is usage-based and depends on the plans of the customer for the consumption of Puhuri services. The overall goal is to make sure that jointly built services are providing the required functionality for the target customers and are cost-efficient. Building services in a multi-tenant fashion however typically is more expensive and hence resource pooling efficiency comes after a certain number of customers.

Our further assumption is that price distribution might not always be fully even, i.e. infrastructures that serve 50 users should be paying proportionally less than infrastructures serving 5000. This is to motivate the adoption of Puhuri services and generally corresponds to common practice.

The exact pricing at the moment of writing is not set due to ongoing contract negotiations, however, we present a **generic model** with pricing of **approximate** order of magnitude. The model is applicable to the initial services planned to be provided: Puhuri AAI and Puhuri Core.

The model first calculates overall costs per year, e.g:

Puhuri Service X Costs (example)	
Outsource Component A	50000
Puhuri internal costs for Component B	10000
Total costs per annum	60000

Figure 5: Puhuri service cost - please note that numbers are only for demonstration purposes

We then break service into packages based on the customer tiers, and provide hypotheses of the proportion of costs that each tier should have for the total costs. We also calculate the baseline pricing for the tier. Units can be e.g. number of users or allocations, depending on the service.

Client packages	Proportion of costs	Baseline pricing (example)
<100 units	1	600
<500 units	4	2400
<2000 units	10	6000
<4000 units	15	9000
Unlimited units	70	42000

Total weight	100
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Figure 6: Puhuri baseline pricing - please note that numbers are only for demo purposes.

The real pricing comes when we have a concrete number of customers for each of the packages. For example, for a basic scenario of 1 customer from each group we get an effective price equal to the baseline pricing:

Packages	Packages (clients)	Total baseline revenue (example)	Pooling coefficient	Effective price per client package (example)
<100 units	1	600	1.00	600.00
<500 units	1	2400	1.00	2,400.00
<2000 units	1	6000	1.00	6,000.00
<4000 units	1	9000	1.00	9,000.00
Unlimited units	1	42000	1.00	42,000.00

Figure 7: Puhuri package pricing - please note that numbers are only for demo purposes

For situation with a single larger customer, it would need to cover also other levels and effective cost would be higher:

Packages	Packages (clients)	Total baseline revenue (example)	Pooling coefficient	Effective price per client package (example)
<100 units	0	0	1.43	0.00
<500 units	0	0	1.43	0.00
<2000 units	0	0	1.43	0.00
<4000 units	0	0	1.43	0.00
Unlimited units	1	42000	1.43	60,000.00

Figure 8: Puhuri pricing mode - please note that numbers are only for demo purposes.

With the growth of the number of customers, the pricing for different packages drops, e.g.:

Packages	Packages (clients)	Total baseline revenue (example)	Pooling coefficient	Effective price per client package (example)
<100 units	5	3000	0.33	195.44
<500 units	3	7200	0.33	781.76
<2000 units	5	30000	0.33	1,954.40
<4000 units	2	18000	0.33	2,931.60
Unlimited units	3	126000	0.33	13,680.78

Figure 9: Puhuri cost & pricing - please note that numbers are only for demo purposes

Of course, with a growth of the number of customers certain shared costs might start increasing too, e.g. SLA with external providers like GÉANT might not be sufficient or increased costs on Puhuri

Support need to be covered. We believe that an annual review of pricing might be sufficient to address this issue.

3.3. Discussion & future scenarios

Puhuri will seek funding from Customer fees and from other funding sources. NeIC Puhuri 2 project is due to last until May 2025. LUMI is operating longer than that.

Aim is to implement attractive pricing, which is due to cover the necessary costs.

4. Puhuri stakeholders and their expectations

Puhuri 2 project interviewed²³ primarily LUMI consortium as they are allocating resources for the LUMI EuroHPC supercomputer based on their ownership. We also reached out to other stakeholders. To provide a better feeling of the state of Puhuri at the moment of writing of this deliverable, below are summarised counters for different groups of stakeholders. Please note that numbers change over time.

Stakeholders	Current amount in production	Comment
Service Providers	1	Additional service providers have been integrated in beta.
Service offerings	152	Not all offerings are in active use.
Resource Allocators	~30	
Active allocations	~450	
Number of end-users with that had allocations	~750	
Organisations of end-users	~180	Based on the uniqueness of email domains
Puhuri Portals	10	Only Puhuri hosted services are included.
Integrated national portals	2	1 more has been integrated and due to be launched from next year.

Figure 10: Groups of stakeholders - Puhuri

²³ Interviews will be published after the consent of respondents

Other stakeholders are:

- NeIC as project owner
- EuroHPC JU allocating the resources and defining the policies for EuroHPC HPC

Stakeholders are invited to the quarterly Puhuri Reference Group meetings.

4.1. Feedback from the stakeholders

This section describes a summarization of the feedback received from the respondents.

Description of the respondents

The respondents are all involved with Puhuri but to different extent. Some of the respondents are very much invested in the way of being represented in various groups, being involved from the start of the Puhuri project and the development and some of the respondents consume the service but are not heavily involved otherwise with the Puhuri project.

Visions, benefits and the future

Comparing the vision with the Puhuri representative and the respondents, the visions for the future of Puhuri correspond with each other. The Puhuri project aims to expand into more customers and this seems to correspond with the vision that the current respondents have. Both the Puhuri representative and the respondents are aware that Puhuri needs to find its way on the European research infrastructure landscape and its future legal entity.

Both the Puhuri representative and the respondents would like to see sustainability in future for Puhuri. Respondents that have been more heavily involved with the development since the beginning have discussed the sustainability and governance issue in more detail during the interviews. Also mentioned is that Puhuri must find its way in the European infrastructure landscape, have a cost model and contract forms.

The respondents are generally happy with the services provided by Puhuri and are happy with the first line support, the clean and modern interface and how flexible it is to access Puhuri. The major benefits that the respondents brought up during the interviews is the federation with frameworks for identities and that this is flexible. They also mentioned that you can manage resources in a simple way. They also like the first line support, and also like where you can see how much resources have been used. They like the clean, modern and clear interface. One of the respondents also said that Puhuri is mandatory for solving multi allocator multinational usage. Also that Puhuri has the ability of confining the information of different parties so that the allocated state is not exposed to each other.

The respondents also mentioned that there is a benefit of having the Puhuri outsourcing of the project management, the technical solution that the portal is maintained and you don't need to use your own staffing for maintenance and development.

Other benefits are the integration with LUMI and the seamless access to the infrastructure and the potential Puhuri has and possibility of being used by many services. They also brought up that Puhuri is GDPR compliant.

Feedback on further improvements

The Puhuri representative brought up the application of review functionality as something missing in the Puhuri Portal, something that some of the respondents also brought up during the interviews. Some things that the respondents are missing from Puhuri is that the interface is a bit confusing. One of the respondents had to have a colleague helping out in the start. Feedback also included that the workflow can be confusing and you have to click around a lot. One respondent would like to have schedule allocation in a calendar period automatically, but needs to do this currently manually. When inviting team members it takes time to find out how to invite via email. One respondent would like to have a search field to find if a person is connected to a project and one of the respondents would also like to increase the period of when an invitation to the portal is valid. The workflow was also discussed that Puhuri needs a cleaner and clearer workflow and more intuitive.

One of the issues that was discussed by several of the service providers was that it is difficult to see how much resources have been spent and the usage data. The accounting is different from the usage shown. They would like to have ways to track the usage of resources and evaluate resource applications. There was also feedback on user rights, customizability for which rights each user has, not just PI but also co-PI members. Some of the service providers also mentioned that they would like to have a review management process.

One of the service providers also mentioned that Puhuri does not need additional features added but instead needs to be streamlined.

The service providers also addressed some other issues, one thing is sustainability and future governance, that Puhuri needs to integrate more customers, finding its way in the European landscape.

Both the Puhuri representative and the service providers are aware that if Puhuri would not exist, then service providers would have to manage something equal to the service of Puhuri themselves with costs involved on staffing, application, AAI system and developing system themselves.

Business models and contracts

Most of the service providers found it difficult to discuss business models and contracts, saying that they usually forward these questions to an expert within the subject. However, the contract template was mentioned.

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5. References

Adomeit, Marina, Happonen, Kalle, Laitinen, Jarno, Livenson, Ilja, Nyholm, Juha, Saar, Ahti, & Sjöström, Anders. (2021). *Implementation of Puhuri core functionalities (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727686>

Edelmann, Erik, Nyholm, Juha, Saar, Ahti, Happonen, Kalle, Livenson, Ilja, Sjöström, Anders, Zaiaev, Sergei, Gasels, Jefirms, Laitinen, Jarno, & Engström, Kent. (2022). *Puhuri Deliverable D4 Accounting and Reporting (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361321>

Engström, Kent, Adomeit, Marina, Livenson, Ilja, Nyholm, Juha, Saar, Ahti, Sjöström, Anders, Zaiaev, Sergei, Happonen, Kalle, & Laitinen, Jarno. (2021). *Puhuri Deliverable 3 - LUMI Integration to Puhuri (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5747047>

Laitinen, J., Adoimet, M., Happonen, K., Anders Sjöström, Lassi, M., Engström, K., Saar, A., Livenson, I., & Nyholm, J. (2020). *Requirements and architecture plan for Puhuri*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.428877>

LUMI EuroHPC supercomputer web page. (referred 15.12.2022). <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/>

LUMI Documentation - Logging in with SSH client. (referred 15.12.2022). <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/firststeps/loggingin/>

Puhuri Documentation. (referred 15.12.2022). <https://puhuri.neic.no/>

Puhuri Documentation - Organization and project management, The Dedicated portal guide. (referred 15.12.2022). https://puhuri.neic.no/user_guides/user_guide_dedicated/organization_and_project_management/#creation-of-projects

Puhuri Documentation - Organization and project management, The Shared portal guide. (referred 15.12.2022).

https://puhuri.neic.no/user_guides/user_guide_shared/organization_and_project_management_shared/#creation-of-projects

Appendix 1 - Nomenclature

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Nomenclature is important in order to make sure to have the same understanding of the concepts and information objects central to the Puhuri project. Terminology can be used to find commonalities and semantic interoperability between the national portals' or different service providers definitions, the definitions used by Puhuri.

Term	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) (also used alternative term IAM). A set of various services to register a user to get a Puhuri ID, authenticate (i.e. to get the user identity) to use the integrated Resources (services), and provide means for the resources provider to grant access to the eligible users.
Accepted Terms of Service	A boolean value indicating if the Person has accepted the terms of service for a given resource.
Accounting	A set consisting of the aggregation of the allocation of resource components to a project, and the actual consumption of allocated resource components within a project.
Allocating Body	The entity that decides on the allocation of the resources to projects. There are multiple allocating bodies but at least one per participating country.
Allocating Body Member	A person or persons able to create projects and allocate resources according to the respective allocating bodies decisions.
Allocation	The right to access a resource and use of a resource component from a start date to an end date and to an extent of the offering components are defined for a project.
API	Application Programming Interface. An interface for machine-to-machine data transfer.
Authentication	Process of getting information regarding who the user is.
Offering component	A component of the Service offering that can be configured by Resource Allocator for a specific Allocation. Different resources may consume these at different rates. Offering components are defined for all resources that have accountable resources. Offering components can have minimal and maximal safety limits defined by service providers.

GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation is a regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.
Project lifespan	The time period over which a project can have an allocation from one or more of service offerings . Project starts at the creation by Resource allocator and may have an end date, when requests for termination are sent to all of the service providers that have provided resources to the project.
Member	A member of a project.
MyAccessID	AAI services operated by GÉANT eduTEAMS including user registration, profile management and for user authentication the Idp Proxy with identity provider search function. Puhuri AAI is integrated to the Idp Proxy.
MyAccessID Account	A representation of a unique real person with a unique identifier (aka CUID) within MyAccessID AAI. Containing the contact information and institutional details for the person.
National Portal	A National Portal is an existing portal that can communicate with Puhuri Core through an API and by which researchers can apply for the use of, and be given access to, a resource. If present it is to be used instead of the Puhuri portal.
Principal Investigator	A principal investigator (PI) is a person responsible for, and manager of, a Project.
Project	A project is an object with one or more allocations of one or more resources. The project can have a number of allocations assigned to it. A project can have zero or more of PIs, c-PI and members. The project can be time limited by the lifespan.
Puhuri AAI	A system for user registration and issuing Puhuri Account and AAI proxy for connecting IdPs and services. Puhuri AAI acts as a proxy to MyAccessID.
Puhuri Core	The central service that keeps track of the projects, service offerings, resource allocators, allocations and membership information. It also offers service providers APIs for sharing accounting and credential information.
Puhuri Portal	The portal to be used in absence of a National Portal with at least the same functionality as a National Portal.
Puhuri Services	The aggregation of Puhuri Core, Puhuri Support, Puhuri Stats, Puhuri AAI, Puhuri Portal, and corresponding APIs.
Puhuri Stats	A portal for Service Providers and Resource Allocators to see aggregated statistics about Puhuri Services.
Usage Reporting	The process by which the utilisation of allocated resource components in terms of consumed offering components within a project by members of the project is presented to stakeholders.
Role	Set of permissions for making decisions in Puhuri Portal or National portal.

Service Account	Also called a Robot Account - A User Account which is not representing a real person, but a machine. However, it must have associated contact information to responsible persons.
User ID	A user is the entity (a real person or a machine) that uses the Resource. A User can belong to zero, one, or more Projects.